

Reaction-driven formation of SiC–ZrC interlayers for high-strength joining of monolithic CVD β -SiC and SiC_f/SiC composites

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Abstract

A reliable joining method for monolithic CVD β -SiC and SiC_f/SiC composites was developed using an in-situ formed ZrC-SiC interlayer. A ZrSi₂-C powder mixture was employed as the raw material, and joining was performed via field-assisted sintering technique. Initially, the joining conditions were optimised for CVD β -SiC ceramics by varying the interlayer composition (ZrSi₂ and ZrSi₂ + C) and processing temperature (1400 - 1650°C). The joints produced using a non-stoichiometric mixture of raw materials (ZrSi₂:C = 1:1.5) at 1600°C exhibited a uniform interlayer and the highest flexural strength (~270 MPa). Furthermore, the joints maintained structural integrity up to 1400°C and retained a flexural strength of 125 MPa at 1500 °C, without decomposition of the ZrC-SiC interlayer. Finally, the optimised joining conditions were successfully applied to SiC_f/SiC composites, yielding a shear strength of ~87 MPa, which exceeded that of the reference unjoined materials.

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1. Introduction

Silicon carbide (SiC) based-ceramics have been considered high-temperature structural materials for aerospace and nuclear energy applications due to their unique combination of excellent properties, such as a relatively high melting point, high-temperature mechanical properties, high thermal conductivity, excellent thermal shock resistance, and good oxidation resistance [1–4]. Moreover, chemical vapour deposited (CVD) β -SiC and silicon carbide fibre-reinforced silicon carbide matrix composites (SiC_f/SiC) possess a high neutron irradiation resistance, which makes them primary candidates for high-temperature components, such as structural materials in advanced fusion reactors and fuel cladding materials in fission reactors [5]. However, the fabrication of large and complex SiC-based ceramic components remains challenging. Consequently, the practical utilisation of these materials is strongly dependent on the development of reliable joining techniques. Indeed, joining represents one of the most cost-effective approaches for extending the application range of SiC-based ceramics [6,7].

Various joining techniques have been explored for SiC-based ceramics, including metallic brazing [8], solid-state diffusion bonding with metallic interlayers [9], metal-ceramic hybrid interlayer [10], glass-ceramic joining [11], direct bonding [12], and MAX phase joining [13]. Nevertheless, joints intended for extreme environments must withstand a combination of ultra-high temperatures, severe thermal gradients, chemical reactivity, radiation exposure, and mechanical loading. Therefore, in addition to practical considerations such as joint strength and processing feasibility, the development of joints with excellent high-temperature mechanical performance, oxidation resistance, irradiation stability, and a coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) compatible with SiC substrates remains a critical challenge [14,15].

To achieve strong and reliable joints under such demanding conditions, recent efforts have focused on minimising residual stresses arising from CTE mismatch between the SiC substrates and the interlayer materials. In the past decade, significant attention has been devoted to MAX phases as joining interlayers for monolithic SiC and SiC-based composites, following the work of Morozumi et al. [16], who attributed the high joint strength in Ti-based systems to the formation of Ti₃SiC₂ [17–19]. Ti₃SiC₂, belonging to the group of MAX phases (where M is an early transition metal, A is an A-group element, and X is either C or N) [20], has been used as an interlayer in various forms, including pre-synthesised powders [17], tapes [18], or

pre-sintered foils [21]. However, a rather high coefficient of thermal expansion of Ti_3SiC_2 ($\text{CTE} \sim 9.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [22] when compared to SiC ($\text{CTE} \sim 4.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [23], can lead to the development of significant thermal residual stresses and subsequent cracking at the joint interface. Zhou et al. [24] investigated the thermal residual stresses between Ti_3SiC_2 and SiC by Raman spectroscopy and reported that thermal residual stresses up to 1 GPa form upon cooling from 1300°C to room temperature. To mitigate this issue, multilayer interlayers, such as SiC/TiC/ Ti_3SiC_2 /TiC/SiC have been designed to reduce stress gradients via the in-situ formation of TiC ($\text{CTE} \sim 7.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [25]. This approach resulted in a flexural strength of 155 MPa, significantly higher than the 99.1 MPa reported for SiC/ Ti_3SiC_2 /SiC joints [26]. Similarly, Fitriani et al. [27] incorporated 10 wt% SiC whiskers (SiC_w) into the Ti_3SiC_2 interlayer and introduced a TiC gradient layer, achieving a flexural strength of 199 MPa in SiC_f/SiC joints. Subsequent work by Teng Yu et al. further improved the flexural strength to 256 MPa using 15 wt.% SiC whiskers in monolithic SiC joints [28]. Despite these advances, the CTE mismatch associated with Ti_3SiC_2 and TiC interlayers remains relatively high for demanding high-temperature applications.

Zirconium carbide (ZrC) is a well-known ultra-high temperature ceramic material with a comparatively lower CTE ($6.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [29]), making it a promising candidate as an interlayer material for SiC joining. ZrC possesses a high melting temperature ($\sim 3550^\circ\text{C}$), high elastic modulus ($\sim 400 \text{ GPa}$), high hardness ($\sim 20 \text{ GPa}$), relatively low density (6.7 g/cm^3), good thermal ($\sim 50 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) and electrical conductivity ($63 - 75 \times 10^{-6} \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$), good thermo-mechanical stability at elevated temperature, and excellent neutron transparency [29-31]. However, due to its poor sinterability and limited oxidation resistance, SiC has been used as an additive for the development of ZrC-based ceramics [32, 33].

Various processing routes have been demonstrated to fabricate ZrC-SiC composites. For example, Antou et al. produced ZrC-SiC composites via Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) of ZrC + SiC powder mixture at 1950°C , under 50 MPa [33], while Feng et al. developed similar materials using reactive hot pressing of ZrH_2 , carbon black, and SiC powders at 1900°C under 32 MPa [32]. Yu et al. reported that ZrC-SiC composites with fine and homogenous microstructures could be synthesised from a $\text{ZrSi}_2 + \text{C}$ powder mixture via SPS sintering at 1750°C under 40 MPa [34]. In addition, wetting studies have shown that ZrSi_2 reacts with SiC substrates to form ZrC at the interface, indicating its suitability for reactive joining processes [35]. Indeed, two recent works have reported the in situ reactive joining of SiC with $\text{ZrSi}_2 + \text{SiC}$ [36] and $\text{ZrSi}_2 + \text{C}$ [37] interlayers. However, these studies are confined to monolithic SiC and

primarily demonstrate the feasibility of joining; the high-temperature mechanical performance of the in situ-formed ZrC phase, critical to joint integrity, remains largely unexplored.

Therefore, the present study aims to develop an in-situ formed ZrC-SiC ceramic interlayer for joining monolithic CVD β -SiC ceramics and SiC_f/SiC composites to themselves using ZrSi₂ and ZrSi₂-C powder mixtures. The joining process was first optimised using monolithic CVD β -SiC, and the optimised conditions were subsequently applied to SiC_f/SiC composites. The influence of joining temperature on microstructure evolution and mechanical performance of the joints was systematically investigated at both room and elevated temperatures.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1. Materials preparation

Fully dense monolithic CVD β -SiC ceramics (99.9995% purity, 3.21 g/cm³ density, Dow Chemical Company, USA) and SiC_f/SiC composites (Keraman® SiC/SiC manufactured by CVI process with UBE Tyranno S fibres, supplied by BJS Composites GmbH) were used as substrate materials. The CVD β -SiC specimens were machined into rectangular bars (~ 15 × 6 × 10 mm³), and the joining surfaces (6×15 mm²) were ground and polished to a final finish using a 1 μ m diamond suspension. The SiC_f/SiC composites were supplied in square plates (~ 10 × 10 × 3 mm³), and were joined along the 10 × 10 mm² surfaces without further machining or polishing.

Commercial ZrSi₂ alloy powder (99.5% purity, 2.12 μ m average particle size, ABCR GmbH, Germany) and carbon black powder (~325 mesh, Vulcan PF, CS Cabot, USA) were used as raw materials for the interlayer. Three compositions were investigated for joining of monolithic SiC substrates: (i) pure ZrSi₂, (ii) a stoichiometric mixture of ZrSi₂ and carbon black (molar ratio ZrSi₂:C = 1:3), and (iii) a non-stoichiometric mixture (ZrSi₂:C = 1:1.5). Table 1 shows the compositions of the interlayers, along with the corresponding joining temperatures. The stoichiometric ratio was selected based on the following reaction:

Powder mixtures were prepared using a planetary ball mill (PM100, Retsch) for 2h at 250 rpm, with a ball-to-powder ratio of 10:1. A 50 ml tungsten carbide (WC) jar and WC balls (3 mm diameter) were used as milling media, with isopropanol as the solvent. After ball milling, the suspensions were dried using a rotary vacuum evaporator and subsequently dried in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 18 h.

2.2. Joining procedure

The powder mixtures were dispersed in isopropanol to form a slurry containing 30 wt.% solids, without the addition of binders or additives. The slurry was applied to the joining surfaces of both substrates by manual brushing. The coated piece of SiC material was then placed on another, and the assembly was placed in a graphite die (20 mm diameter). The joining process was carried out using pressure-assisted SPS (DSP 507, Dr. Fritsch GmbH, Germany). The samples were heated to the target temperatures (Table 1) at a rate of 100°C/min under an Ar atmosphere, while a constant uniaxial pressure of 15 MPa was applied. The dwell time at the joining temperature was 5 min, followed by cooling to room temperature at 50 °C/min.

Table 1. Composition of interlayer materials and joining temperatures.

Substrates	Interlayer materials	Joining Temperatures (°C)
CVD β -SiC	Pure $ZrSi_2$	1400, 1500, 1600, 1700
CVD β -SiC	Stoichiometric mixture e ($ZrSi_2:C = 1:3$)	1500, 1700
CVD β -SiC	Non-stoichiometric mixture ($ZrSi_2:C = 1:1.5$)	1400, 1450, 1500, 1550, 1600, 1650
SiC _f /SiC composite	Non-stoichiometric mixture ($ZrSi_2:C = 1:1.5$)	1600

2.3. Characterisation of the joints

The microstructures of the joint cross-sections were investigated using SEM (AURIGA Compact, Zeiss) after grinding and polishing to a final finish of 3 μ m using diamond suspension. Moreover, the microstructures and chemical compositions of the interlayers were investigated using a transmission electron microscope (TEM, Talos™ F200x, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), equipped with an EDS detector. Phase identification was carried out using selected area electron diffraction (SAED). Thin foils for TEM analysis were prepared using a focused ion beam (FIB) technique (Helios 5 CX, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA).

The flexural strength of the CVD β -SiC joints, as well as that of unjoined CVD β -SiC used as the reference material, was evaluated in air at room temperature using a four-point bending test on a universal electromechanical testing machine (Instron 8862, USA). The beams with the dimensions of $\sim 2 \times 3 \times 20$ mm³ were sectioned from the joined as well as the reference

(unjoined) SiC blocks ($\sim 15 \times 6 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$). To minimise stress concentration, the edges on the tensile side were chamfered at 45° , and the tensile surfaces were polished to a mirror finish (final $3 \mu\text{m}$ diamond suspension). The inner and outer spans were 10 and 20 mm, respectively, and the cross-head speed used for loading was 0.5 mm/min. At least five specimens were tested for each condition.

High-temperature flexural strength was measured using the same four-point bending configuration for the optimised joining process, i.e. CVD β -SiC samples joined at 1600°C with a $\text{ZrSi}_2\text{:C}$ ratio of 1:1.5. The tests were performed on a universal electromechanical testing system (Messphysik-Zwick/Roel) equipped with a vacuum/inert gas furnace. Samples were preloaded to 20 N and heated at $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to the testing temperature, under an argon protective atmosphere, followed by a 15 min dwell to ensure thermal equilibrium. Loading was then applied at 0.5 mm/min until failure. At least three specimens were tested at each temperature.

The shear strength of the SiC_f/SiC joints was evaluated using a single lap offset shear test on a compression testing machine (SINTEC D/10) at room temperature. Copper spacers were positioned on opposite sides of the joint to create the offset configuration, following the method described in [21]. A cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min was applied. The apparent shear strength was calculated by dividing the maximum load by the joining area ($\sim 100 \text{ mm}^2$). Five SiC_f/SiC specimens joined at 1600°C were tested.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Joining of monolithic CVD β -SiC using a pure ZrSi_2 interlayer

Fig. 1 presents the SEM images of monolithic CVD β -SiC joined using a pure ZrSi_2 interlayer at different temperatures. At the joining temperature of 1400°C (Fig. 1a), no significant interfacial reaction was observed, and the interlayer remained predominantly composed of ZrSi_2 . Since the joining temperature is approximately 220°C below the melting point of ZrSi_2 , the interlayer remained in the solid state, limiting atomic interdiffusion and chemical interaction with the SiC substrate. As a result, a discontinuous and weakly bonded interface was formed, indicating insufficient interfacial contact and bonding at this temperature.

Increasing the temperature to 1500°C (Fig. 1b) promoted interfacial reactions between ZrSi_2 and the SiC substrate, leading to partial dissolution of SiC into the interlayer and the formation of a continuous ZrC layer at the interface (see the EDS results in supplementary material, Fig. S1). However, the central region of the interlayer still contained a significant amount of unreacted ZrSi_2 phases. The presence of these residual disilicide phases is

undesirable, as it is expected to degrade the high-temperature mechanical performance of the joints. Moreover, thermal residual stresses arising from the mismatch in CTE between ZrSi_2 (CTE $\sim 8.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [38]) and the ceramic phases (ZrC and SiC) may further deteriorate joint integrity at elevated temperatures.

At 1600°C (Fig. 1c), the fraction of ZrC grains within the interlayer increased, while the amount of residual ZrSi_2 decreased. The elevated temperature enhanced the reaction between ZrSi_2 and SiC , resulting in increased dissolution of the substrate and improved infiltration of the interlayer, according to:

Further increasing the joining temperature to 1700°C , which exceeds the melting point of ZrSi_2 (1620°C), intensified this reaction, leading to the formation of an interlayer composed predominantly of ZrC , with no detectable Si-containing phases by EDS (see the supplementary material, Fig. S2). The presence of pores within the interlayer is attributed to the evaporation of in situ-formed free silicon, as well as the extrusion of Si liquid phases under the applied pressure (15 MPa). This also explains the reduced thickness of the interlayer in samples joined at 1700°C , when compared to those joined at lower temperatures.

Fig. 1. Secondary electron SEM images of the polished cross-sections of monolithic CVD-SiC samples joined with pure ZrSi_2 by SPS at different temperatures: (a) 1400°C , (b) 1500°C , (c) 1600°C , and (d) 1700°C .

3.2. Joining of monolithic CVD β -SiC using a stoichiometric ZrSi_2 -C interlayer

In order to control the dissolution of the SiC substrate into the interlayer, a stoichiometric amount of carbon black ($\text{ZrSi}_2:\text{C} = 1:3$) was added to ZrSi_2 to promote the formation of a SiC - ZrC composite interlayer, according to Reaction (1). Fig. 2 shows the SEM images of the monolithic CVD-SiC specimens joined using this stoichiometric interlayer at two different temperatures. At 1500°C (Fig. 2a), limited interaction between the interlayer and the CVD β -SiC substrate was observed, as indicated by a distinct and well-defined interface. At the same time, the interlayer remained highly porous under these conditions. At 1700°C (Fig.

2b), the interfacial reaction became more pronounced, resulting in the formation of a composite interlayer consisting of SiC grains embedded within a ZrC-rich phase matrix. Additionally, a nearly continuous SiC layer formed at the interface, acting as a diffusion barrier that suppressed further dissolution of the SiC substrate. These results clearly confirm that the addition of carbon effectively inhibits the dissolution of SiC into molten ZrSi₂, in contrast to the behaviour observed with a pure ZrSi₂ interlayer (Fig. 1d).

Despite this improvement, the interlayer remained porous, indicating insufficient densification of the ZrC–SiC composite under the applied joining conditions (1700 °C, 15 MPa). Thermodynamically, Reaction (1) is favourable even at room temperature, with only minor variation in Gibbs free energy up to 1700 °C. Therefore, the formation of reaction products (ZrC and SiC) occurs prior to the melting of ZrSi₂, limiting the availability of a liquid phase that could promote densification. In addition, at elevated temperatures, partial softening and/or localised melting of residual ZrSi₂, combined with the applied pressure, can lead to extrusion of the ZrSi₂–C mixture from the joint region, as also observed in Fig. 1, thereby contributing to the apparent reduction in joint thickness.

Yu L. et al. reported that fully dense ZrC–SiC composites derived from stoichiometric ZrSi₂–C mixtures required processing at 1750°C under 40 MPa for 10 min [34]. However, in the present work, the absence of a sufficient liquid phase, combined with the relatively low applied pressure (15 MPa), resulted in incomplete densification and the retention of porosity within the interlayer.

Fig. 2. Secondary electron SEM images of the polished CVD β -SiC cross-sections joined using a stoichiometric mixture of ZrSi₂-C at different temperatures: (a) 1500°C, and (b) 1700°C.

3.3. Joining of monolithic CVD-SiC with a non-stoichiometric ZrSi₂-C powder mixture

To enhance the densification of the ZrC-SiC composite interlayer, the carbon content was reduced to half of the stoichiometric amount ($\text{ZrSi}_2\text{:C} = 1\text{:}1.5$), resulting in a non-stoichiometric composition relative to Reaction (1). Fig. 3 shows the SEM images of monolithic CVD β -SiC joints produced using this interlayer over a temperature range of 1400°C - 1650°C.

A lower carbon content significantly improved the interaction between the interlayer and the CVD β -SiC substrate at lower temperatures. Initially, the interlayer consisted of a ZrSi₂-C powder mixture placed between two SiC substrates. At joining temperatures of 1400 °C and 1450 °C (Figs. 3a and 3b), which are below the melting point of ZrSi₂, the interlayer remained predominantly in the solid state. Under these conditions, a fine-grained and relatively dense microstructure was formed, consisting mainly of ZrSi₂ along with partially reacted phases such as ZrC and newly formed SiC. The resulting joint region appears uniform and nearly pore-free, indicating improved particle rearrangement and limited solid-state diffusion-controlled reactions.

At 1500°C (Fig. 3c), a continuous SiC layer was formed at the interface, while the interlayer consisted of three distinct phases: SiC (dark grey), ZrC (bright), and residual ZrSi₂ (light grey). The EDS analysis also revealed a minor presence of ZrO₂ impurities (see the supplementary material, Fig. S3). The in-situ formed ZrC particles were distributed both within the residual ZrSi₂ matrix and within SiC grains, consistent with the relative phase proportions predicted by Reaction (1) and the molar ratio of ZrSi₂ and C.

As the joining temperature increased from 1500°C to 1550°C the fraction of residual ZrSi₂ decreased significantly, while the ZrC content increased (Fig. 4). This reduction in intermetallic ZrSi₂ is beneficial, as its relatively low melting temperature may negatively affect high-temperature joint performance. In addition, the presence of ZrSi₂ contributed to the formation of transverse cracks due to thermal expansion mismatch with SiC and ZrC. At lower temperatures (1400°C and 1450°C), these cracks propagated across the interlayer and occasionally extended into the substrate (Fig. 3a and 3b). At 1500°C, finer cracks were observed (Fig. 3c), predominantly in ZrSi₂-rich regions (Fig. 4a); however, the in-situ formed SiC interfacial layer effectively inhibited crack propagation into the substrate. At 1550°C, only a limited number of fine cracks remained (Fig. 3d), mainly located at ZrC/ZrSi₂ interfaces (Fig. 4b).

Fig. 3. Back-scattered SEM images of the polished CVD β -SiC cross-sections joined using a non-stoichiometric $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayer at different temperatures: (a) 1400, (b) 1450, (c) 1500, (d) 1550, (e) 1600, and (f) 1650 °C.

By increasing the temperature to 1600°C (Fig. 3e), no cracks were observed within the joint region. The interlayer was primarily composed of SiC and ZrC, with only a trace amount of residual $ZrSi_2$. While the thickness of the interlayer remained approximately 130 – 140 μm for the samples joined between 1400°C and 1550°C, it decreased significantly to $\sim 60 \mu m$ for the joint processed at 1600°C. This reduction is attributed to enhanced interfacial reactions and partial dissolution of the SiC substrate, accompanied by infiltration of the interlayer into the substrate. Since the joining temperature (1600°C) was very close to the melting temperature of $ZrSi_2$ (1620°C), the formation of a transient liquid phase is possible [39]. This liquid phase promotes mass transport and reaction kinetics, facilitating the consumption of residual $ZrSi_2$ phases. Under the applied pressure (15 MPa), the liquid phase is partially expelled from the joint region and subsequently solidifies at the periphery, resulting in a thinner and more homogeneous interlayer with minimal residual intermetallic phases.

At 1650 °C (Fig. 3f), these effects became more pronounced. Although the thickness of the interlayer remained the same ($\sim 60 \mu m$), increased dissolution of the SiC substrate and deeper infiltration of the interlayer were observed. No residual Zr–Si phases were detected, indicating complete consumption of $ZrSi_2$ through reactions with both C and SiC (Reactions (1) and (2)). However, the extensive expulsion of the liquid phase led to increased porosity

within the interlayer. This liquid phase is attributed to Zr–Si-rich compositions formed during the joining process, as the applied temperature exceeds the melting point of ZrSi_2 . Although initial reactions occur in the solid state, any remaining or newly formed Zr–Si phases can locally melt at $1650\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, generating a transient liquid phase that is subsequently expelled under the applied pressure.

Fig. 4. Back-scattered SEM image of the interlayer formed at a) 1500 and b) 1550 °C.

TEM was employed to further analyse the phase composition of the interlayer. Fig 5 shows a high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) image of the interlayer in the CVD β -SiC joints prepared with ZrSi_2 -10 wt.% C at $1600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The EDS elemental mapping revealed the presence of four distinct phases, consistent with SEM observations. The SAED analysis (Fig. 5) confirmed that β -SiC (dark grey phase) is the dominant phase within the interlayer. ZrC was identified as the second major phase (bright phase), while a small amount of residual ZrSi_2 (light grey phase) was also detected. In addition, isolated oxide inclusions were identified as ZrO_2 .

Oxygen was also detected within ZrC-rich regions. The measured interplanar spacing of the ZrC (002) planes was 2.351 \AA , which is lower than the theoretical value of 2.447 \AA (based on a lattice parameter of 4.894 \AA ; PDF 04-008-5918). This deviation is attributed to the partial substitution of carbon atoms by oxygen atoms within the ZrC lattice, as oxygen has a smaller atomic radius (152 pm) than carbon (170 pm), leading to lattice contraction [40,41]. The presence of oxygen is likely associated with contamination introduced during powder processing and ball milling.

Fig. 5. HAADF image of the SiC joined using a $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayer and corresponding elemental mapping results.

3.4. Joining mechanism of monolithic CVD β -SiC using $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayers

The joining mechanism of CVD β -SiC using $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayers is governed by a sequence of temperature-dependent in situ reactions, phase transformations, and transport phenomena, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 6. At low temperatures, the interlayer remains largely unreacted, consisting of $ZrSi_2$ and carbon powders with limited interfacial interaction due to poor wettability and sluggish diffusion kinetics. With increasing temperature, $ZrSi_2$ becomes thermodynamically unstable in the presence of carbon and SiC, initiating interfacial reactions that form ZrC and Si-rich phases. These reactions preferentially occur at particle contacts and triple junctions, progressively forming a heterogeneous mixture of ZrC, SiC, and residual Zr-Si phases. Although this initial reaction layer enhances local bonding, it remains discontinuous and therefore provides only limited densification [35].

In stoichiometric compositions, the rapid consumption of $ZrSi_2$ via solid-state reactions results in the direct formation of a SiC-ZrC composite prior to melting, thereby rendering the joining process dominated by solid-state sintering. Due to the inherently diffusion-limited nature of this process, densification remains incomplete and residual porosity is retained within the interlayer [34]. In contrast, the use of a non-stoichiometric composition ($ZrSi_2:C = 1:1.5$) modifies the reaction pathway by delaying full silicide consumption and enabling the formation

of a transient Zr–Si liquid phase at elevated temperatures (≥ 1600 °C). The presence of this liquid phase significantly enhances wetting of the SiC substrate, accelerates mass transport through liquid-phase diffusion, and promotes particle rearrangement, thereby facilitating pore elimination and interlayer densification [36,37].

Moreover, the liquid phase activates a dissolution–reprecipitation mechanism, in which SiC partially dissolves into the liquid and subsequently reprecipitates, resulting in microstructural homogenization and refinement of the SiC matrix. Concurrently, $ZrSi_2$ reacts with carbon to form finely dispersed ZrC, leading to a uniform distribution of ZrC within the interlayer and contributing to the formation of a dense SiC–ZrC composite. At the interface, the in-situ formation of a continuous SiC layer promotes strong chemical bonding while acting as a diffusion barrier that suppresses excessive substrate dissolution and mitigates crack propagation [35,37,42]. As a result, at optimal temperatures (~ 1600 °C), a dense and homogeneous interlayer with minimal residual silicide phases and reduced porosity is achieved. However, further temperature increase (e.g., 1650 °C) leads to excessive Zr–Si liquid phase formation and its expulsion under applied pressure, causing interlayer thinning, pore formation, and compositional inhomogeneity, ultimately deteriorating the joint quality.

Fig. 6. Schematic illustration of in-situ reactions within the $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayer during joining of CVD β -SiC.

3.5. Flexural strength of monolithic CVD β -SiC joints using $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayers

The flexural strength of the CVD β -SiC joints as a function of joining temperature is presented in Fig. 7a. A dependence of mechanical performance on the joining temperature corresponding to previously described microstructural development of the interlayer can be observed. The flexural strength increases progressively with joining temperature from 1400°C to 1600°C , reaching a maximum of approximately 270 MPa at 1600°C , then decreases by about

30% at 1650°C. The strength improvement at 1600°C can be attributed to enhanced interfacial reactions, improved interlayer densification, and reduced residual Zr–Si phases, as discussed in the previous sections. For comparison, significantly lower flexural strengths have been reported for SiC joints produced using alternative interlayers. For instance, a flexural strength of 126 MPa was reported for joints obtained using Ti as an interlayer [43], while joining of commercially available SiC using the ternary carbide Ti_3SiC_2 resulted in a strength of approximately 110 MPa [17]. In another study, a maximum strength of 163 MPa was achieved using Ti_3SiC_2 tapes combined with an in situ-formed TiC gradient layer via FAST [25]. In this context, the maximum strength achieved in the present work (~270 MPa) is considerably higher, indicating the effectiveness of the $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayer system in promoting strong interfacial bonding and improved mechanical performance.

Fig. 7. (a) Room-temperature flexural strength of CVD β -SiC joints produced using non-stoichiometric $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayers by SPS at different joining temperatures; (b) high-temperature flexural strength of CVD β -SiC joints obtained at 1600 °C.

At lower joining temperatures, the presence of cracks, incomplete reactions, and residual intermetallic phases adversely affects the mechanical performance, resulting in reduced strength. In contrast, the joint produced at 1600°C exhibits a dense and homogeneous SiC–ZrC interlayer with minimal defects, resulting in superior load transfer and mechanical integrity.

However, further increasing the joining temperature to 1650°C results in a marked decrease in flexural strength. This reduction is primarily associated with increased porosity within the interlayer, caused by excessive liquid phase formation and its expulsion under applied pressure, as well as enhanced dissolution of the SiC substrate. These microstructural changes compromise the structural integrity of the joint and reduce its load-bearing capability.

Based on these results, the optimal joining temperature of 1600°C was identified and selected for high-temperature mechanical testing. The high-temperature flexural strength of the

joints produced at 1600°C is shown in Fig. 7b. The results demonstrate that the joints maintain excellent mechanical stability up to 1400°C, with only a moderate decrease in strength. Even at 1500°C, a flexural strength of approximately 110 MPa is retained, indicating good thermal stability and structural integrity of the SiC–ZrC interlayer.

The gradual reduction in strength with increasing testing temperature is attributed to thermally activated deformation and possible softening of residual Zr-Si phases. Nevertheless, the absence of abrupt strength degradation up to 1400°C confirms the robustness and suitability for high-temperature applications.

Over the past few decades, considerable effort has been devoted to developing reliable joining strategies for SiC-based ceramics, particularly through the use of MAX-phase interlayers. It was reported that the CVD β -SiC joints fabricated using pre-sintered Ti_3SiC_2 interlayers exhibited a maximum flexural strength of approximately 220 MPa at room temperature, which could be retained up to 1000°C [13]. In comparison, the present study demonstrates that joints produced via the in-situ formation of a SiC–ZrC interlayer not only achieve comparable room-temperature strength (~220–270 MPa), but also exhibit improved thermal stability at elevated temperatures. Specifically, the joints retain significant mechanical integrity up to 1400°C and maintain reasonable strength even at 1500°C. This enhanced high-temperature performance can be attributed to the superior thermal stability and lower coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch of the SiC–ZrC interlayer, as well as the absence of low-melting intermetallic phases.

The results presented indicate that the proposed in-situ-formed SiC–ZrC interlayer provides a more thermally robust alternative to conventional MAX-phase-based joining approaches. Consequently, this joining strategy represents a promising route for the fabrication of SiC-based components intended for extreme environments, such as advanced nuclear and aerospace systems.

3.6. Fractography analysis

Fractographic analysis was conducted to further understand the failure behaviour of the joints and to correlate the mechanical performance with the observed microstructures. Representative fracture surfaces are shown in Fig. 8.

For joints produced at lower joining temperatures ($\leq 1500^\circ\text{C}$), failure consistently occurred along the joining interface (Figs. 8a–b). In these cases, relatively large fragments of the interlayer were clearly observed on both sides of the fractured specimens, indicating that crack propagation took place within the interlayer or along the interfacial region. This

behaviour is consistent with the presence of residual Zr–Si phases, incomplete reactions, and microstructural defects, such as porosity and cracks, which all weakened the joining area and promote interfacial failure.

In contrast, the joint fabricated at 1600°C exhibited a significantly different fracture behaviour (Fig. 8c). Failure occurred entirely within the SiC substrate, with no evidence of interlayer material on the fracture surfaces. This observation indicates that the interlayer and the joint interface possess higher strength than the surrounding substrate, confirming the superior mechanical integrity achieved under these joining conditions. This result is in excellent agreement with the maximum flexural strength measured for this sample.

In the case of high-temperature testing, the interlayer material was again observed on both sides of the fractured specimens (Fig. 8d), indicating that failure occurred within the interlayer region. This suggests that, although the joints exhibit good thermal stability and retain significant strength at elevated temperatures, the interlayer becomes the weakest component under these conditions. The reduction in strength at high temperatures may be associated with thermally activated processes, such as softening of residual phases or degradation of interfacial bonding.

Fig. 8. Fracture surfaces of monolithic CVD β -SiC joints produced using a non-stoichiometric $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayer at (a) 1400°C, (b) 1500°C, (c) 1600°C tested in four-point bending at room temperature; (d) joint fabricated at 1600°C and tested at 1400°C in a vacuum.

3.7. Joining of SiC_t/SiC composite using a non-stoichiometric ZrSi₂-C interlayer

Based on the optimisation of joining parameters for monolithic CVD β -SiC, the non-stoichiometric $ZrSi_2$ -C interlayer ($ZrSi_2:C = 1:1.5$) and a joining temperature of $1600^\circ C$ were selected for the joining of SiC_f/SiC composites. Under these conditions, successful joining of the composites was achieved using the same processing route.

Fig. 9 presents the microstructure and corresponding EDS elemental maps of the SiC_f/SiC joints. A continuous and fully ceramic ZrC-SiC interlayer with an average thickness of approximately $90\ \mu m$ was formed between the composite substrates (Fig. 9a). A uniform microstructure of the interlayer, consisting of ZrC and SiC, is shown in Fig. 9b. Notably, significant infiltration of the interlayer into the porous regions of the SiC_f/SiC composites was observed (Figs. 9a and (d)). This infiltration led to the formation of in situ SiC-ZrC phases within the near-interface region of the composite, effectively filling pores and enhancing local densification (Fig. 9a and 9d).

The formation of these phases, which exhibit coefficients of thermal expansion similar to that of the SiC_f/SiC composite, contributes to improved stress distribution and mechanical integrity in the joining region. Importantly, despite the application of a uniaxial pressure of 15 MPa during joining at a relatively high temperature ($1600^\circ C$), no evidence of SiC fibre damage was observed, indicating that the processing conditions are compatible with the structural integrity of the composite reinforcement.

The beneficial effect of interlayer infiltration is further reflected in the mechanical performance of the joints. The apparent shear strength of the joined SiC_f/SiC composites reached 86.9 ± 6.0 MPa, which is significantly higher than the interlaminar shear strength of the reference, unjoined composite (45 MPa, according to the supplier BJS, Germany). This substantial improvement can be attributed to the combined effects of interfacial bonding and reinforcement of the porous composite structure through infiltration and in situ phase formation.

In summary, these results demonstrate that the proposed joining approach is not only effective for monolithic SiC but also highly suitable for SiC_f/SiC composites, offering the additional advantage of locally strengthening the composite through controlled infiltration

Fig. 9. (a–c) SEM micrographs of SiC_f/SiC composite joints produced using a non-stoichiometric $\text{ZrSi}_2\text{-C}$ interlayer (10 wt.% C) at 1600 °C, showing the formation of a ZrC-SiC interlayer and its infiltration into the porous composite; (d) corresponding EDS elemental maps (Zr, Si, C, and O).

3.8. Joining mechanism of SiC_f/SiC composites using $\text{ZrSi}_2\text{-C}$ interlayers

The joining mechanism of SiC_f/SiC composites using the non-stoichiometric $\text{ZrSi}_2\text{-C}$ interlayer is illustrated schematically in Fig. 10. Similar to the case of monolithic CVD $\beta\text{-SiC}$, the process is governed by in situ reactions between ZrSi_2 , carbon, and the SiC matrix, leading to the formation of a ZrC-SiC composite interlayer. However, due to the intrinsic porosity of the SiC_f/SiC composites, an additional infiltration-driven mechanism plays a key role [44]. During heating, the decomposition and reaction of ZrSi_2 generate Si-rich liquid phases, which enhance wetting and promote mass transport along the interface and within the porous composite. These liquid phases enable capillary-driven infiltration into inter-bundle regions and fibre/matrix interfaces, facilitating intimate contact and bonding [39,44]. Simultaneously, chemical reactions between Zr, Si, C, and SiC lead to the formation of ZrC and secondary SiC , resulting in a multiphase interlayer [42]. Consequently, the joining mechanism involves a combination of reactive infiltration and in situ phase formation, producing a dense SiC-ZrC composite interlayer (region a) and infiltrated zones within the SiC_f/SiC substrates (region b),

as shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Schematic illustration of the joining mechanism of SiC_f/SiC composites using a non-stoichiometric ZrSi₂-C interlayer: evolution from the initial powder interlayer to (a) a dense ZrC-SiC composite interlayer and (b) an infiltrated SiC_f/SiC region reinforced by in situ formed ZrC-SiC phases.

At elevated temperatures (1600°C), the presence of a transient Zr-Si liquid phase enhances wetting and facilitates capillary-driven infiltration of the interlayer into the porous regions of the composite. This infiltration results in the formation of ZrC-SiC phases within the near-interface region, effectively filling pores and creating a graded transition zone between the interlayer and the composite substrate. As illustrated in Fig. 10, this process leads to the development of (i) a dense ZrC-SiC interlayer and (ii) an infiltrated composite region reinforced by newly formed ceramic phases.

The formation of this graded structure significantly improves load transfer across the joint and reduces stress concentrations at the interface. Furthermore, the close match in coefficients of thermal expansion between the ZrC-SiC phases and the SiC_f/SiC composite minimises residual thermal stresses. Unlike in monolithic CVD β-SiC, where the joining is primarily interface-controlled, the joining of SiC_f/SiC composites is therefore governed by a combined mechanism of reaction bonding and infiltration-assisted reinforcement.

As a result, the joint region becomes locally strengthened, which explains the observed increase in apparent shear strength compared with the reference composite. This behaviour highlights the dual role of the interlayer, acting not only as a joining medium but also as a reinforcing phase within the porous composite structure.

Conclusions

A reliable joining approach for monolithic CVD β -SiC and SiC_f/SiC composites was developed using an in situ formed ZrC-SiC ceramic interlayer derived from ZrSi₂-C powder mixtures via spark plasma sintering. The main findings can be summarised as follows:

- A non-stoichiometric ZrSi₂-C mixture (ZrSi₂:C = 1:1.5) enabled the formation of a dense and homogeneous ZrC-SiC interlayer during joining of CVD β -SiC.
- The optimal joining temperature was identified as 1600 °C, at which a crack-free interlayer with minimal residual Zr-Si phases was obtained, resulting in the highest room temperature flexural strength (~270 MPa).
- The fractographic analysis revealed that only for the joints at 1600°C, fracture occurred in the base material. In all other cases, the crack path alternates between the joining surfaces through the interlayer.
- The CVD β -SiC joints exhibited excellent high-temperature performance, maintaining structural integrity up to 1400 °C and retaining a flexural strength of ~110 MPa at 1500°C, demonstrating the thermal stability of the ZrC-SiC interlayer.
- At higher testing temperatures of optimised joints, the weakest place is at the interface, contrary to room temperature.
- Successful joining of SiC_f/SiC composites was achieved under the optimised conditions found for CVD β -SiC. Interlayer infiltration into the porous composite resulted in in-situ reinforcement of the near-interface region, leading to a significant increase in the apparent shear strength of ~87MPa, compared with the reference material at ~45 MPa.

Overall, the proposed in situ SiC-ZrC interlayer provides a robust and thermally stable joining solution for SiC-based ceramics. The combination of strong interfacial bonding, reduced thermal mismatch, and infiltration-assisted reinforcement makes this approach particularly promising for high-temperature applications in aerospace and nuclear reactor environments.

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Naser Hosseini – conceptualization; data curation; investigation; visualization; writing – original draft, **Zdeněk Chlup** – methodology; validation, funding acquisition, **Carla Malinverni** – investigation, **Alexandra Kovalčíková** – investigation, **Pengxing Cui** – investigation, **Monika Tatarková** – investigation; data curation, **Valentina Casalegno** – methodology; investigation, **Xiaobing Zhou** – investigation; validation; funding acquisition, **Milena Salvo** – investigation; validation, **Ivo Dlouhý** – validation; funding acquisition; formal analysis, **Peter Tatarko** – conceptualization; supervision; validation; visualization; funding acquisition; writing – review & editing

Data Availability

Data supporting the findings of this study are available in the Zenodo repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19742989>.

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